

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOTIVATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of motivation as it is an influential factor in teaching a foreign language. The success of learning depends on whether or not the learners are motivated. Motivation drives learners in reaching learning goals. Without student motivation, there is no pulse; there is no life in the class. When we learn to incorporate direct approaches to generating student motivation in our teaching, we will become happier and more successful teachers. The issue of motivation is so important that other considerations about teaching methodology seem to pale in comparison. It is important to think about motivation as the essence of language teaching because of the stark realities of learning foreign languages for most of our students.

Motivation is one of the important aspects of second language acquisition. Motivation is a kind of desire for learning. It is very difficult to teach a second language in a learning environment if the learner does not have a desire to learn a language. Taken into consideration from that aspect, to be able to make the learner active and desirable in learning process gains importance [4].

An important role in motivation is played by interest: interest in learning, interest in activity. In turn, the interest depends on the content of the training. If the child is interested, he is attentive in the lesson, active. And, on the contrary, if it is not interesting, it is passive, indifferent to what is happening. Thus, the teacher should investigate the reasons for low

motivation and determine possible directions for its improvement and development.

According to Dornyei and Ushioda "the word motivation derives from the Latin verb *movere* meaning "to move" [2]. However, the term "motivation" refers to a process that stimulates learners' behavior or arouses someone or people to step forward to take an action. In other words, one can say that it is a force that pushes a person to do an action, often inspired by an idea, an event, or a goal.

In language education especially in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, motivation has not been studied as a separate independent scientific problem until the second half of the twentieth century. But educators put

forward scientific hypotheses about the adaptation of the teaching process to students and the conduct of it in an interesting way.

Even if the phrase motivation was not used in advanced pedagogical ideas which are concentrated in didactic principles, this problem was tried to be solved.

Motivation is a powerful factor in the realization of the goals and objectives of education and in order to awaken the necessary internal motivation.

Foreign scientists as Dornyei, J.Entwistl, G.Rosenfeld, W.Knorzer, D.Mc.Clelland, C.Coferand, Apley, J.Atkinson, Feather, Harmer have made their contributions in the study of the issue of motivation. Motivation for the study of foreign languages in students begins to form not only from the early stages of higher education, but also from school years, which is more realized through the personal characteristics and professional skills of the teacher.

Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation are a widely cited distinction of motivation in learning a language, whether it comes from inside and outside. Harmer points out that intrinsic motivation is that which comes from within the individual in which a person might be motivated by the enjoyment of the learning process itself or by a desire to make themselves feel better. The extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is that which comes from outside factors, for example, the need to pass an exam, the hope of financial reward, or the possibility of future travel [3]. Thus, the intrinsic motivation in English language learning is about the enjoyment of language learning itself, whereas extrinsic motivation is driven by external factors

such as academic requirements or rewards and punishments. As a result, with intrinsic motivation, a language learner is encouraged to do a task or engage in a classroom activity purely because of enjoyment or fun, whereas with extrinsic motivation, in contrast, a language learner is encouraged to do a task or engage in a classroom activity mainly because doing so will yield some kind of reward or benefit upon completion. In an educational program, it is claimed that intrinsic motivation is more powerful than extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is considered to result in better learning outcomes than extrinsic motivation. However, in an EFL program, most of the language learners engaging in learning activities are driven by external motivations. Harmer points out that even where the original reason for taking up a language course, for example, is extrinsic, the chances of success will be significantly enhanced if the students come to love the learning process [3].

A distinctive feature of students' attitude to the study of a foreign language is that it is recognized by many as a very difficult science. Zimnyaya notes that this process requires a study of motivation. That is, it is necessary for the learner to fully understand why he began to learn a foreign language and set himself a clear goal.

The motivation of students in teaching foreign languages should be seen as a weapon that increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Education is an opportunity for people to do what they did not do before, to try to understand what they did not understand before, sometimes to be another person [1].

The style of pedagogical activity has a significant influence on the formation of the teaching motivation. There are teachers with an authoritarian style who primarily rely on negative motivation. In such cases, the students' activities are motivated by a desire to avoid all sorts of troubles: punishment from the teacher or parents, poor

grades, etc. This motivation, when you stop using reinforcements and punishments, quickly fades away. Democratic style it promotes the development of internal, more stable motivation and is characterized by the delegation of rights and responsibilities [5].

According to the research on motivation and its importance in education we can conclude that modern

psychologists, educators and methodists put forward a common opinion that the quality and result of fulfillment of the activity is primarily conducted with the desire and need of the individual as a result of the analysis. Motivation as an activity is exactly directed towards a specific goal, it is the force that determines the means and methods to achieve the goals.

Motivation in relation to educational activities of students is the main source of activity and increase the effectiveness of the educational process. As a result, motivation helps for the future professional activities of students' formation and to the development a foreign language.

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